

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE GRAMMAR IN TEACHING RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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**Ten S.K.
Rahimova A.I.**

Senior Teachers,
Russian Language Interfaculty Department,
National University of Uzbekistan

Abstract:

Keywords:

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Nowadays learning the languages is one of the most important issues, as it is required in any profession. Teaching grammar is still one of discussed topics of language learning area. Linguistics give various methods of teaching grammar. Accordingly, the language can't be learnt without studying grammar of the language. As stated by famous scientist V.K.Pavlenko "Grammar is not a code of rules." But some people say that the utility of teaching grammar is doubtful in learning Russian language. They say that the students who study grammar are very often able to solve grammar exercises but cannot produce the right speech. Teaching grammar had a very important place in the past. It was commonly believed that helping to the learners to learn Russian language its grammar must be taught first. It was also believed that without knowing and mastering grammatical rules of Russian language, one cannot learn to speak and write it. Slowly it was realized that correct usages go on changing from time to time.

Also, I think that, grammar knowledge helps the students in the correction of mistakes and improvement of a written work. One can't learn a foreign language accurately only through a person of unconscious assimilation. So, grammar is necessary for the students. In this paper, my aim is to bring the attention of the language teacher as well as the learner to the real benefits of grammar in teaching Russian language.

Today the tendency is to say, "Forget grammar. Teach the language people speak, and let your students have fun!" I don't agree with this attitude, and will explain why. Student who goes to live in a foreign country, will learn to speak the language by just listening and interacting with others. His brain is young and powerful enough to pick up the language he is exposed to while respecting all the

aspects of this language – grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation. They can learn the grammar within these approaches

Approaches of Teaching Russian Language Grammar:

There are three approaches of teaching grammar:

1. Deductive approach
2. Inductive approach
3. Inductive Deductive approach
4. Incidental approach

1. Deductive Approach: In deductive approach the teacher uses a grammar text book. He tells his students rules or definitions and explains those with the help of examples then he gives exercise and ask his pupils to apply the rules.

2. Inductive Approach: In inductive approach the teacher first presents or takes

the example from the students then comes on theory or concept.

3. Inductive Deductive Approach: This approach, by the name shows that this is the synthesis of the both methods above. This method can remove the limitation of the both methods. The teacher following this method will first present the examples before his students, then he will explain them or analyses them. And there he will try to see that students can draw some conclusion and then teacher will give the rules. But here the teacher does not stop. He then gives new examples and asks his pupils to verify the rules. This method of teaching grammar provides very successful as it becomes practical, real and scientific. It proves very well because it is very psychological following all the accepted maxims of teaching and the students are not forced to cram the rules.

4. Incidental Method: Grammar teaching in this method is done during the teaching of a textbook or composition writing. The teacher explains complex sentence pattern. But the method at times disturbs the teaching of a textbook or composition writing.

To conclude, I want to say that, the value of grammar teaching is important in Russian language teaching fields. Grammar is the basic of Russian language. It is not acquired naturally, but in order to learn, it needs to be instructed. While learning grammar, some students may have a more analytical learning style than others, but if students hope to use Russian language accurately, and likely these students will learn at different rates.

In short, grammar is necessary in Russian language teaching.

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